

EFFECTS OF KOMBUCHA AS AN ANTIBACTERIAL ON BURNS

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The field of biological sciences is very interesting to be pursued but one of the specifications in biological sciences is the field of microbiology. The field of microbiology has a variety of aspects that can be applied to our lives or become a solution or that we are familiar with life hacks. Microbiology is a study engaged in the field of microbes, as well as bodies of renik. The specialty of microbiology is not only used by those who pursue pure biological studies and education but also used in various fields such as health, nursing, midwifery, acupuncture, pharmacy, medicine, and so on (Harti, 2015). In addition to the field of microbiology, health can develop into virology, bacteriology, mycology, food microbiology, soil microbiology, industry, or specific sciences on the utilization of microbes (Fifendy, 2017). In the field of microbiology obtained an understanding of the smallest creatures that even as can not be seen with the naked eye, but these small creatures turned out to bring enormous benefits and impacts to human life. Microbiology itself is a science that can be coupled with other studies such as ecology, physiology, biochemistry, physics, and others, but this paper will study the relationship of biological sciences with animal physiology with the aim of improving solutions to diseases that are often found in animals and humans and has a chance to see the real results of existing theories. In addition, the mixing of these two studies is expected to provide new research results in this field

Kombucha is a fermentation product that utilizes a microbial starter namely SCOBY (*Symbiotic Colony of Bacteria and Yeast*) consisting of *Acetobacter xylinum* bacteria and *Cerevisiae saccharomyces* yeast. The culture media of kombucha making that is often used is tea containing tannin compounds, saponins, flavonoids, and so on. The fermentation process in kombucha usually lasts for 2-4 days, kombucha can be useful as an antibacterial, repair intestinal microflora, antifungus, and others (Winda, 2021). The use of sweet tea media is known to contain glucose that supports the growth of kombucha culture that converts sugar into alcohol followed by the production of chemical substances such as gluconic acid, acetic acid, lactic acid, vitamins, amino acids, and antibiotic substances (Romanna &Evi, 2019). Kombucha mushrooms will inter parasitize between acetic acid bacteria and osmophilic yeast species in the coating on sweet tea fermentation, but the composition contained in kombucha will depend on the source of carbon and inoculum in fermentation, as well as other factors such as kombucha substrates, time, temperature, process, and microorganisms present in the starter (Mercury &Sumarni, *in* Shinta 2021). Active compounds such as terpenoids, alkaloids, flavonoids, essential oils, phenols, and curcumin have antimicrobial character and this content can be found in kombucha (Duryatmo, 2003 *in* Adila &Agustien, 2013).

Kombucha is included in the drink that has antioxidant content that is sourced from the basic ingredients of making kombucha (Nur *et al*,2018). Kombucha tea also contains various chemical compounds such as vitamin B1 in the form of tannin, vitamin B2 in the form of riboflavin, vitamin B3 niacin, vitamin B6 cyanocobalamin, vitamin C, polyphenol, and so on. Each compound has a variety of health benefits such as fat metabolism by vitamin B3 that can lower LDL while increasing HDL, reducing vascular disease and coronary heart disease. In addition, the catechin content of polyphenols plays a role in the prevention of high blood pressure and reduce the occurrence of cholesterol hoarding in the blood through the process of

disposal of feces, in addition to kitakin and many more kombucha tea content whose benefits have not been directly studied (Tana & Djaelani, 2015). Kombucha is also known to have benefits for blood detoxification, normalizing intestinal activity, improving the body's immune system, and improving the body's metabolism in general (Karyantina, 2019).

Burns are wounds caused by fire, hot water, contact with hot or cold materials, chemicals, and electric current, which can be divided by the depth of burns, namely superficial, partial-thickness, and deep partial-thickness (American Burn Association, 2011 in Putri & Asparini, 2017). Burns exposed to open air for long time hypoperfusion or necrotic tissue have the opportunity to be an ideal place for bacterial colonization due to a nutrient-rich and warm environment. The presence of bacteria in burns will inhibit the healing process of wounds before the invasion of tissues from toxin secretions directly or indirectly from vital cells (exotoxins). This poison will produce local necrosis that disrupts the balance of mediators required in the wound healing process (Putri & Asparini, 2017). There have been several studies finding the presence of normal flora on the skin, airways, or human gastrointestinal tract that often form colonies in burns, usually consisting of several aerobic bacteria namely *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and so on. (Christiawan & Perdanakusuma, 2010). Some studies show the benefits of kombucha as an antibacterial that is able to inhibit the growth of bacteria such as *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and others, these bacteria are known to be bacteria that are often found as contaminants in burns (. Inhibition of bacterial colony growth caused by damage in structural membrane components of bacterial cells composed of proteins and lipids, damage to these cell membranes will interfere with the process of transporting nutrients in contaminant bacterial cells (Volk & Wheeler, 1991 in Sari, et al, 2013). Pathogenic bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus* have the ability to infect the skin, bones, lungs, heart, or systemic infections, therefore the content of flavonoids and phenol is known to be a chemical compound that has the potential to become antibacterial (Rahmadeni et al, 2017).

Based on the previous paragraph statements, kombucha has a variety of benefits that have the potential to be a solution to various health problems found at this time due to the content of chemical compounds that have many roles such as antibacterial, antioxidant, cancer prevention, cholesterol, diabetes, and others. This is an opportunity to present new solutions that can be applied to the community. In addition, the content and SCOBY kombucha that has a variety of benefits but not yet done a lot of research specifically can open the potential for the emergence of various new theories in this field with a variety of approaches or methods that can be presented to the subject or object of research. It can also be seen that the field of biology can be matched with other studies in various fields such as biochemistry, pharmaceutical medicine, physiology, pathology, and so on.

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